

Supplementary table 5. Adjusted absolute risk of CS by fetal heartbeat at admission

Supplementary Table 5 Adjusted absolute risk of CS by fetal heartbeat at admission, estimated from multivariable logistic regression models

	Antepartum stillbirths		Intrapartum stillbirths		Live births	
	Adjusted Absolute risk*	95% CI	Adjusted Absolute risk*	95% CI	Adjusted Absolute risk*	95% CI
Fetal heartbeat at admission						
Positive	0.24	0.19-0.29	0.44	0.41-0.48	0.25	0.25-0.25
Negative	0.15	0.13-0.17	0.33	0.31-0.36	0.31	0.29-0.34
No information	0.40	0.33-0.47	0.59	0.54-0.65	0.66	0.65-0.67

*Adjusted for maternal age, parity, previous pregnancy outcome, number of antenatal care visits, previous CS, multiple pregnancy, maternal antenatal complications [hypertensive disorders, antepartum hemorrhage, diabetes, malaria, cardiac/renal disease, gestational diabetes, HIV status], referral status, baby's presentation, macrosomia, gestational age, and country